

hydrazone, m.p. 157°. **2** (0.2 g) with 2 N H₂SO₄ (1.4 ml) yielded gelatinous D-allose (**4**; 0.12 g), m.p. 128° [α]_D+7° (H₂O); it formed an osazone, m.p. 173°.

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Chemical Examination of *Buddleia neemda*

B. Ham.

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IN connection with our work on plant pigments¹, phytochemical investigation of *Buddleia neemda* B. Ham. (Syn. *B. asiatica* Lour.; loganiaceae)² has been undertaken. *B. neemda* is a very common shrub occurring throughout India and is used as an indigenous drug in the treatment of skin diseases. Literature survey reveals that the flowers of this plant have been investigated earlier³. We now report the results of chemical examination of the aerial parts (stems and leaves) of this plant on which no work has been done so far.

The air dried powdered aerial parts (stems and leaves) of *B. neemda* was successively extracted with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) and chloroform. The concentrated petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) extract was chromatographed over silica gel. Elution of the column with benzene–chloroform (3 : 1) mixture afforded yellow needles, C₁₇H₁₄O₆ (*M*⁺ 314), m.p. 280°, crystallised from benzene. It gave greenish blue colour with ferric chloride and responded magnesium–hydrochloric acid test for flavonoids. It was found to contain two methoxy groups as indicated by Zeisel experiment and exhibits $\lambda_{\max}$ 255, 310 nm; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3200 (br, bonded-OH), 1650, 1605 and 1580 cm⁻¹ (chelated α,β -unsaturated C=O). These spectral data in conjunction with the fact that the compound forms a monomethyl ether, C₁₈H₁₆O₆ (*M*⁺ 328), m.p. 160° on treatment with diazomethane, and a dimethyl ether, C₂₀H₁₈O₆ (*M*⁺ 342), m.p. 188° on reaction with dimethyl sulphate reveals that the compound is a dihydroxydimethoxyflavone. Finally, the flavone was characterised as 5,7-dihydroxy-3',4'-dimethoxyflavone from the comparison of physical properties of this compound and its mono- and dimethyl derivatives respectively with those of the aglycone of 3',4'-dimethylfluteolin-7-O- β -D-glucopyranuronide⁴, 7,3',4'-trimethylfluteolin⁵ and 5,7,3',4'-

tetramethylfluteolin⁶. Incidentally, it appears to be the first report of isolation of this flavone from natural source.

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Chemical Constituents of *Nephrolepis tuberosa*

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IN the course of our investigation on different Indian ferns having insecticidal and biological activity, we undertook the systematic chemical investigation of a hitherto uninvestigated plant, *Nephrolepis tuberosa* (Fam.: *Pteridophytes*), popularly known as *Pani Amla*, which grows abundantly in the Eastern Himalayan region.

The light petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) extract of the powdered stem and leaves of *N. tuberosa* upon chromatography over silica gel afforded β -sitosterol.

The chloroform extract of the defatted stem and leaves was fractionated into acidic and neutral fractions. The neutral fraction was chromatographed over silica gel. Elution with benzene–chloroform (8 : 2) yielded a compound NT-1 C₃₀H₅₂O₈ (*M*⁺ 444), m.p. 258–60°, [α]_D+20.94°, $\nu_{\max}$ 3360 cm⁻¹ (OH) and 1450, 1380 cm⁻¹ (*gem*-dimethyl). Absence of any olefinic proton signal and presence of characteristic signals at δ 0.79–1.20 for eight methyl groups coupled with positive L.B. test suggested compound NT-I to be a saturated

pentacyclic triterpene¹. Mass spectrum of NT-1 exhibited fragments at m/z 444 (M^+), 426 (M^+-H_2O) 411, 383 and 189 (100%). The mass fragmentation pattern coupled with other data suggested its identity with that of dustannin (1)².

In conformity with the structure, 1 formed a monoacetate, $C_{32}H_{54}O_3$ (M^+ 486), m.p. 198–200°, with acetic anhydride and pyridine. Its ir spectra ν_{max} 1 720, 1 250 (O.CO.CH₃) and 3 520 cm^{-1} (tert-hydroxy). The pmr spectra showed besides the usual peaks for methyl and methylene protons, a singlet at δ 2.05 for acetyl functions. The mass spectra exhibited characteristic fragments at m/z 486 (M^+), 426 (M^+-60), 408 ($M^+-60-18$) and 189 (100%) consistent with structure 2. However, final confirmation could not be made for want of authentic sample.

The mass left after extraction chloroform was extracted with methanol at room temperature. Methanol was then removed and the residue partitioned between water and ethyl acetate. Ethyl acetate fraction upon chromatographic purification yielded compound NT-2, $C_{38}H_{60}O_6$ (M^+ 576), m.p. 288–89° [α]_D –33.95° (pyridine), identified as β -sitosterol- β -D-glucoside³. It formed an acetate, $C_{48}H_{88}O_{10}$, m.p. 168–70°, [α]_D –23.91° (CHCl₃) and furnished β -sitosterol, m.p. 139–40°, on hydrolysis with 5% ethanolic HCl.

- 1; $R_1 = \beta$ -Me, $R_2 = \alpha$ -Me, $R_3 = \alpha$ -OH, $R_4 = R_5 = H$,
 $R_6 = \alpha$ -Me, $R_7 = OH$
 2; $R_1 = \beta$ -Me, $R_2 = \alpha$ -Me, $R_3 = \alpha$ -OAc, $R_4 = R_5 = H$,
 $R_6 = \alpha$ -Me, $R_7 = OH$
 3; $R_1 = R_2 = R_3 = R_7 = H$, $R_4 = \beta$ -Me, $R_5 = \alpha$ -Me,
 9,11-dehydro

The petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) extract of rhizomes of *N. tuberosa* afforded compound NT-3, $C_{30}H_{50}$ (M^+ 410), m.p. 167–70°, which exhibited in its mass spectrum, besides the molecular ion peak, other prominent peaks at m/z 395, 257, 243 (100%) and 231. The base peak at m/z 243 coupled with the appearance of a one-proton multiplet at δ 5.4 suggested its identity as fern-9(11)-ene (3)⁴ which was finally confirmed by comparison with an authentic sample.

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Flavonoids from the Leaves of *Buchanania lanzan* (Anacardiaceae)

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IN consideration of interesting biological properties of many species¹ of *Buchanania* rich in flavonoid constituents, investigation on flavonoid constituents of several species² of this genus was undertaken. In the present paper we report the isolation and characterisation of kaempferol-7-*O*-glucoside (BLG-I), quercetin-7-*O*-rhamnoside (BLG-II) and quercetin-3-*O*-rhamnoglucoside (BLG-III) along with quercetin (BL-I), gallic acid (BL-II) and kaempferol (BL-III) which were characterised by their spectral data and comparison with authentic samples.

The leaves (1 kg; collected from Dudh Sagar, Goa) were consecutively extracted with petroleum ether, benzene, acetone and methanol. The acetone extract gave positive colour test for flavonoids. The tlc examination (benzene–pyridine–formic acid, B-P-F, 36:9:5) revealed the presence of three bands which were labelled as BL-I to BL-III in the order of increasing R_f values. They were separated by preparative-tlc (B-P-F) and eluted by acetone. BL-I, m.p. 313–14°; BL-II, m.p. 250 and BL-III, m.p. 276–78°, were characterised as quercetin, gallic acid and kaempferol, respectively, by comparison of their R_f values, m.p., m.m.p., uv, ir and nmr spectra with authentic samples.